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Well-defined Critical Editing: The ‘Manuscribus’ Platform for Manuscript Transcription, Annotation, and auto-Collation

Abstract

"Well-defined Critical Editing" is a topic firmly connected to the "Ontology-based Palaeography"; these two phrasal terms represent a most modern approach on what philologists engage with, that is the graphemic form of a language and the effort one undertakes to produce critical editions.

"Well-defined Critical Editing" describes on one hand the controlled vocabulary still produced worldwide to describe manuscripts themselves, and on the other hand the processes occurring while working with these manuscripts: Transcription, Collation, Editing and Publishing. Analogously, "Ontology-based Palaeography"¹ stands for the infrastructure needed to be developed to support the "Well-defined Critical Editon", that is both firm theoretical basis² and practical solutions.

Ontology-based Palaeography: Relational model and fundamental units (manuscript, stroke, manus, scribe/copyist, codex)

For the "Ontology based Palaeography" any physical medium that supports handwriting, that is handwritten text, is an object, in fact a 3-dimensional object; such a concept is crucial, otherwise handwritten texts of significant importance, e.g. palimpsests, are hard to understand if one perceives manuscripts as 2-dimensional objects. A manuscript, which is an object, as we just mentioned, is also considered a flexible object: for inflexible objects and object parts (for instance, rocks, marbles, woods, etc.), alternative terms have

¹ Guarino (2009: 1-2); Arp, Smith, Spear (2015: 1-4); Duval (2015: 211).

² Maniaci (1996: 241); Duval (2015: 100).

been used over time instead of the term "manuscript": "inscriptions," "rock engravings," "carvings," etc., for reasons that go beyond the scope of this paper.

One might propose to increase such an analysis depth, and acknowledge that a manuscript is not an object, but an object aggregate, bearing other objects on it, large or tiny, constructed from a multitude of materials which in turn have various physical origins. Nevertheless, once such an expansion to the aforementioned analysis is applied, OR and AND conditions are arised:

A manuscript **IS** an object (assertion) => "is-type" relation

OR

A manuscript **IS** an object aggregate (assertion) => "is-type" relation

AND

An object aggregate **HAS MEMBER PART** an object (inference) *OR* another object aggregate => "has-type" relation

This simplified example illustrates the basic logical conditions needed to understand a relational model. Palaeography, Codicology, and consequently Critical Editing are firmly connected to the expansion of this model. Every time a text is transcribed to produce a Critical Editon, we gradually take into our consideration a multiplicity of complex factors.

Ontology metrics: ?	
Metrics	
Axiom	9,229
Logical axiom count	4,847
Declaration axioms count	1,655
Class count	419
Object property count	77
Data property count	78
Individual count	1,038
Annotation Property count	47
Class axioms	
SubClassOf	621
EquivalentClasses	0
DisjointClasses	12
GCI count	0
Hidden GCI Count	0

Image 1: The OHT [Ontology for Handwritten Text] developed at the DH Lab, National and Kapodistrian University of Athens, developed to support a relational model for Palaeography, Codicology and Critical Editing.

Assume a scribe, creating a handwritten text with the aid of a pen or a quill, while some years later another scribe creates additional objects in the very same side of a folium; some centuries later you and your team are trying to unfold the complexity of all these

entities your ancestors created. Imagine any combination you want, but there is no chance that your case does not fall into the following image.

Image 2: Ink filling the cavities of a substrate (e.g. parchment).

According to this image, different “hands” arise in various manuscript regions; thus, a manuscript rather resembles a sponge, as objects (or object aggregates) accumulate in its cavities, the state of which changes over time, e.g. from liquid becomes solid. Let us imagine these solid “ink rocks” (that’s what we perceive as “writing”) existing above – rather, within – the folium we are reading from. The cavities of the sponge we call “manuscript” are filled with these “ink rocks” thanks to various agents-scribes, who placed them, intentionally arranged, on a substrate made of papyrus, parchment, or paper. Other agent-scribes may have emptied these cavities of these “ink rocks” at a specific area or filled some cavities with new material. These “ink rocks” arrangements may form one or more text layers created during not always distinct temporal periods. For manuscripts that were filled, emptied, and refilled with “ink rocks” – the so-called “palimpsests” – time is so crucial that it is added as a fourth dimension to the three dimensions of your manuscript. Given all the above mentioned, any manuscript constitutes a **four-dimensional material object** (or object aggregate) within which there are additional, interconnected, objects (or object aggregates), each related to the other through complex relationships per unit of time. Following such a **palaeographically well-defined manuscript definition** we should, accordingly, accept that the set of all intentionally arranged “ink rocks,” meaningful to a human observer at a specific time, constitute what we call a “text”, composed by a continuous sequence of “ink rocks” the so called “strokes”. A stroke is considered the fundamental unit of the writing found in manuscripts, and is perceived as a meaningful entity either on its own or as part of a whole, formed of more than one stroke, or in relation to other entities (for instance “writing style,” “color,” etc.). Stroke constitutes as well one of the primary means by which the reader of a manuscript identifies a – usually temporally distant – scribe, or more precisely, the scribes of a handwritten text, as quite often we detect more than one “hand”

(manus) in a manuscript. All these infinite details fall into the previously mentioned “relational model” governing all fundamental units present in manuscripts.

Stroke

- ‘is subclass of’ only ‘object’;
- ‘is carrier of at all times’ only ‘manus’;
- ‘has proper continuant part at some time’ only ‘fiat stroke’;
- ‘is member part of at some time’ only ‘stroke and/or fiat stroke aggregate’;
- ‘is bearer of’ some ‘case style’;
- ‘is bearer of’ some ‘color’;
- ‘is located in at some time’ only ‘column’;
- ‘has order’ only xsd:integer.

Image 3: A stroke example as relational model.

To come to our first conclusion: Palaeography is by nature relied on relational models triggering inferences that lead to Critical Editing; But we need a single theoretical and practical model to put together all these entities we just mentioned. This problem has been solved since 2021 thanks to the internationally patented Top Level Ontology which is called Basic Formal Ontology.

Ontology-based Palaeography: (BFO) Basic Formal Ontology supporting relational models

The entities that constitute a manuscript are nowadays strongly supported by the taxonomy and relational model introduced by BFO (Basic Formal Ontology), a Top-Level Ontology (TLO), which provide the root and the main branches to any domain aiming at creating a cohesive theoretical and technical model for research applied to handwritten text and manuscripts. BFO has been actually developed for Sciences and Industry, but became the infrastructure for our DH Lab in Athens aiming at giving a concise response to the following triple argument:

- Firstly, dealing with manuscripts and Critical Editions, primarily requires Transcription; although manuscript Transcription constitutes a significant process, it remains till nowadays a perplexing and insufficiently defined transformation, for a complexity of theoretical and technical reasons. For these reasons manuscript Transcription firmly depends on Critical Editing (and not the opposite, as expected), omitting an amount of crucial information needed for other processes such as the *stemma*³ reconstruction.
- Secondly, while transcribing a manuscript, a most influential process emerges: Annotation. This process hardly manifests itself, nevertheless it is present in subsequent

³ Tarrant (2016: 12-24).

processes, for instance while an editor suggests in the *apparatus criticus*⁴ all readings humanists are familiar with.

- Thirdly, both the Transcription and Annotation processes are crucial not only for Critical Editing and the *stemma* construction, but for numerous other challenging applications that merit research and deal with structured data; We will shortly refer to structured data at the end of this paper⁵.

To address a comprehensive, distinct, cohesive, and feasible solution addressing this triple argument we developed in Athens a system we called *Manuscribus*. This platform supports a well-defined Transcription and Annotation as two distinct, autonomous processes that lead to a well-defined critical edition. But first a few paleographic examples are needed to illustrate Transcription and Annotation processes, which comprised the infrastructure taken into our consideration while designing *Manuscribus*.

Well-defined Critical Editing: Transcription as an independent process

Although Transcription is empirically considered the meticulous process of converting a handwritten text into an updated format – that is into a readable and accessible form allowing the reader to proceed to more evolved, standardized, typed, or printed text –, such a complex practice in fact involves two major, well-defined sub-processes.

- Firstly, the **topological recognition** of the physical area where anything perceived as text has been intentionally located in by scribes, and

- Secondly, **the matching** of any symbol or group of symbols with their appropriate function, which is commonly known as the Annotation process.

Topological recognition

While reading from a manuscript, topological recognition seems obvious for a reader, as it is firmly connected with the specific script applied by a specific scribe; nevertheless, techniques applied over centuries vary, and they deal not only with issues concerning tools and writing styles, but primary with space arrangements. Although not deriving from a manuscript, but from an inscription, the following example depicts the well-known

⁴ Maniaci (1996: 243); Duval (2015: 55); Tarrant (2016: 130-140).

⁵ Maniaci (1996: 241); Duval (2015: 53, 118, 242, 256).

roman square script, the *quadrata*, this elegant form of the capital-type alphabet before the emerging of the Carolingian minuscule⁶.

The Trajan Inscription, Rome

SENATVS POPVLVSQVE ROMANVS | IMP CAESARI DIVI NERVAE F NERVAE | TRAIANO AVG
 GERM DACICO PONTIF | MAXIMO TRIB POT XVII IMP VI COS VI P P | AD DECLARANDVM
 QVANTAE ALTITVDINIS | MONS ET LOCVS TAN[TIS OPER]IBVS SIT EGESTVS

Image 4: Transcription as an independent process (1)

It is obvious that for such short, and dare we say quite primitive text complexity, symbols remain simple, thus their function is considered easily detectable for the reader. Topological information is limited – on row-end and row-beginning – while no word separation is used in general; except of a *punctus simplex*, positioned at the midpoint of the height between two letters, thus it becomes a middle dot, the function of which is *word separator*.

The proposed transcription – in fact quite accurate – intentionally omits many symbols required. Therefore, one might correctly suggest additional symbols, either typographic (that is modern) or even historical. The above transcription tried to avoid these additional symbols; thus, the text intentionally has been left incomplete. In fact, anyone could propose various transcription methods, but all possible transcriptions create the semantic cluster we empirically conceive as Transcription; according to our empirical understanding (which is not well-defined) Transcription does not comprise what we perceive as Edition, which generally is supposed to be a different process than that of Transcription; but I suggest that we wait for such a conclusion.

The following example belongs to the quite famous *uncialis*, a common script for both Latin and Greek manuscripts⁷. Both the Harleianus [lat.] 1775, and the famous Codex

⁶ Petrucci (1992: 42-44, 109-112); Clemens, Graham (2007: 153-154).

⁷ Petrucci (1992: 64-67).

Sinaiticus⁸ consist two of the most well-known manuscripts of this elegant capital script, which is a *scriptio continua*⁹, that is in manuscripts written with this specific script no word separation is generally applied, except for row-endings and row-beginnings: they serve as delimiters, and there are obvious cases in which a large portion of the parchment remains unwritten.

SED UT MINISTRARET | ET DARET ANIMAM SUA[M] |
 REDEMPTIONEM | PRO MULTIS | ET VENIUNT
 HIERICHO | ET PROFICISCENTE EO | DE HIERICHO ET
 | DISCIPULIS EIUS | ET PLURIMA MULTITUDINE |
 FILIUS TIMEI BARTIMAEUS | CAECUS | SEDEBAT
 IUXTA VIAM | MENDICANS | QUI CUM AUDISSET
 QUIA | IH[ESU]S NAZARENUS EST | COEPIT CLAMARE
 ET DICERE | FILI DAVID IH[ESU] MISERERE MEI | ET
 COMMUNABANTUR | ILLI MULTI UT TACERET | AT ILLE
 MULTO MAGIS | CLAMABAT | FILI DAVID MISERERE
 MEI | ET STANS IH[ESU]S PRAECEPTUM | ILLUM VOCARI
 | ET VOCANT CAECUM

Image 5: Transcription as an independent process (2)

Although we tried to be accurate and apply the same transcription technique we applied while transcribing the Trajan inscription, we could not resist some modernities: the curved U-style capital letter for a “vowel representation”, and the angular V-style capital letter for a “consonant representation”, although there is no difference between these two letter-types in a typical *uncialis*. These changes might be considered graphemically insignificant for the specific manuscript, nevertheless none can prevent cases where things might end up quite complicated.

But Brown proposes a totally different transcription, with additional symbols serving as notes on the topological space or as expansions of the letters abbreviated. And suddenly a new need emerges: while applying this method, Brown clearly recognizes a potential

⁸ The Codex Sinaiticus is nowadays scattered in four different libraries: a) British Library, b) Library of the University of Leipzig, c) State Library at St. Petersburg, and d) Library of Mount Sinai Monastery, where all other parts of the manuscript come from. For a digital reunion of the entire manuscript see <https://codexsinaiticus.org>.

⁹ Maniaci (1996: 161); Parkes (2016: 10, 307); Clemens, Graham (2007:83).

alia manus, a second hand¹⁰ which wrote the additional letters at the end of lines 9 and 19. That's a new information a transcriber cannot ignore, thus Brown adopts the use of the sideways reversed slash typographical symbol to annotate what we just mentioned: an *alia manus*, providing to the reader the necessary knowledge on the scribe, or the tool, or even both, an information which normally appears in the *apparatus criticus* of an Edition¹¹.

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1   Sed ut ministraret | et daret animam sua(m). |
   redemptionem | pro multis | Et1 veniunt hiericho2 | et
   proficiscente eo | de hiericho et | discipulis e\i/us3 |
   et plurima multitu\dine/4 | filius Timei Bartimaeus5 |
5   caecus | sedebat iuxta viam | mendicans | qui cum
   audisset quia | Ih(esu)s nazarenus est | coepit clamare
   et dicere | fili David Ih(es)u miserere mei | et
   comminabantur | illi multi ut ta\ceret/6 | at ille multo
   magis | clamabat | fili David miserere mei | et stans
10  Ih(esu)s praecepit | illum vocari | et vocant caecum |7

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Image 6: Brown (1993), *A Guide to Western Historical Scripts from Antiquity to 1600*, p. 24.

So far, we might say that Brown's transcriptional technique remains in the conceptual¹² frame of what we empirically understand as Transcription, although inevitably moved towards some technique belonging to the Edition process. But if one takes a closer look to Brown's transcription, then must admit that just before the symbol representing the *alia manus*, the transcription clearly moves to an additional symbol needed for the logically emerged *forsitan*, because no transcriber can be entirely convinced that there was indeed an *alia manus*¹³ who wrote these specific, additional letters: they seem to be *in margine*. But Brown is aware that the term "margin" seems rather inappropriate for the *uncialis* of the Harleianus because of geometrical reasons: the term "margin" is rather appropriate for a regularized, mostly square or rectangle invisible frame containing a text¹⁴; and that's not the case of the Harleianus' *uncialis*, which does not reach the geometrically elaborated form of Sinaiticus. If one is interested in moving forward to an

¹⁰ Maniaci (1996: 185); Duval (2015: 186, 236).

¹¹ Brown (1993: 24).

¹² Guarino (2009: 4-7).

¹³ To do justice on Brown's excellent work, any typographic attempt to transcribe omits by default a large amount of information needed for the well-defined entities comprising Palaeography and its derivative Editing process, while it is not clear in an *apparatus criticus* whether an *alia manus* comprises a person-shift, a tool-shift, or both. For the Ontology-based perspective we support in this paper, a *manus* is a paleographic entity which depends on both a person and a tool, thus a *forsitan* indication is considered the "average weight" of a transcriber's estimation on both these two entities, see Benetos et al. (2024 forthcoming: section "Stroke, the fundamental unit for handwritten text creation", footnote 5).

¹⁴ Maniaci (1996: 154-155); Muzerelle (1985: 342); Gumbert (2010 draft: 54-61).

Edition, at some point must study the manuscript once again and decide all additional notes emerging from a new investigation. This need will soon lead any transcriber to abandon the Transcription process the way we empirically understand it and move directly to the Edition process; in such a frame and with no digital system supporting Transcription as an independent, not camera ready process, Transcription and Edition start to be more and more fluid, that is not well-defined processes.

Image 7: “Hand” (*manus*) and “margin” in relationship with the logically emerged “certainty degree” (*forsitan*).

Typical challenges demanding transformation while editing but not while transcribing, are syntactic and phonetic traces, the graphemic representation of which clearly appears in line 11 of the Harleianus. Because of syntax, and consequently semantic reasons, it is obvious that the scribe felt the need to graphically denote that the word *caecus* serves as an apposition to the previously mentioned “son of Timaeus”. According to the system the Harleianus’ *uncialis* follows, the word is centered, leaving the rest of the row blank, a technique that rather dictates the appropriate reading of the gospel passage: “The son of Timaeus, who was blind, came to see Jesus”. A double comma should be the direct editorial transformation of these two topological areas, these two large parchment regions that have been intentionally left blank.

The following image depicts an extract from the Parisinus B.N. [lat.] 10313, dating back to the mid-15th century, written in a slight cursive humanistic style¹⁵, and containing the

¹⁵ Petrucci (1992: 175-178).

commentary of Iohannes de Segarellis on Seneca's tragedies¹⁶. Till lately this manuscript was considered the only existing; but it was during 2016 when Romanini's profound research¹⁷ proved that a new manuscript – the Sorbonensis [lat.] 631, dated back to the same period as the Parisinus – also contained Segarelli's commentary.

Image 8: A hypothetical *stemma* based on Romanini (2014), «Per la ricezione di Seneca nel Tre-Quattrocento: due nuovi testimoni dell'Elucidatio tragediarum di Giovanni Segarelli», in *Italia Medioevale e Umanistica* 57, 91-134.

Although Romanini did not explicitly proceed to the graphic representation of this *stemma*, in fact it might be quite the same or slightly different, even if one supposed some more manuscripts and not just too. But for the only two till nowadays existing Segarelli's manuscripts, the important thing is to keep in mind that such a *stemma* clearly takes for granted that the Sorbonensis cannot be a copy of the Parisinus. Nevertheless, in folio 140, lin. 40-41 of the Parisinus, the writing has been topologically structured as illustrated in the following image.

Image 9: Parisinus B.N. [Bibliothèque Nationale de France] lat. 10313, f. 140r, lin. 40-41: a topological structure for a suspicious «saut du même au même».

It is obvious that this topological structure can trigger a copy mistake, which is well-known in French as a *saut du même au même*¹⁸: if the copyist does not pay much attention, it is highly likely that he will continue to copy the text not from the above line but from

¹⁶ We were informed about Segarelli's work by Alessandro Lagioia, Prof. of Latin Literature at the University of Bari Aldo Moro (Italy), who has already published two of Segarelli's commentaries on Seneca's Tragedies.

¹⁷ Romanini (2016: 91-134).

¹⁸ Maniaci (1996: 186); Duval (2015: 233); Tarrant (2016: 10).

the line below, from the specific point comprising the optical equivalent of the topological point located just a line above. Consequently, if a manuscript omits the words included in such a topology that can trigger a *saut du même au même*, “a jump from one point to a similar one”, then this manuscript is probably an apograph¹⁹, and the handwritten book which contains these handwritten leaves might be a *codex descriptus*²⁰. Most recently, during 2020, such a discovery – based on other additional jumps Alessandro Lagioia noticed, triggered changes to the hypothetical Segarelli’s *stemma* previously presented.

N (olim P) = [Parisinus B. N. lat. 10313](#)
[Bibliothèque Nationale de France], saec. XV med.
S₁ = [Parisinus B. S. lat. 631](#)
[Bibliothèque Interuniversitaire de la Sorbonne], saec. XV med.

Image 10: Benetos, and Lagioia (2025, forthcoming), *Iohannes de Segarellis, Elucidatio Tragoediarum Senecae: Medea*. Editio princeps. Quaderni di «Invigilata Lucernis».

To expand this point: no one dares to imagine what analogous findings might concern a most complex *stemma*. The image that follows is an extract from Zwierlein’s remarkable edition on Seneca’s tragedies²¹.

Image 10: Zwierlein (1986), *L. Annaei Senecae tragoediae*, Oxford Classical Texts, p. xviii.

¹⁹ Maniaci (1996: 240); Duval (2015: 55).
²⁰ Maniaci (1996: 239); Duval (2015: 80); Tarrant (2016: 14, 50).
²¹ Zwierlein (1986: xviii).

The *stemma* is impressive, the graphic representation is a unique tool for textual criticism; but no observer is capable of checking the large number of parameters needed to confirm or change such a life work. In any case, manuscript topology plays a crucial role while transcribing and editing a handwritten text, or while constructing a *stemma*; unfortunately, an amount of information remains unworthy because of lacking a tool, where we can assert all factors needed to automatically make all the inferences I just mentioned. If this system existed, the result should be a well-constructed transcription supporting a well-defined critical edition, that's the second conclusion emerged so far.

Symbols and Functions

While transcribing or editing, an additional need emerges: the recognition of handwritten symbols, in fact the function of these symbols we recognize as meaningful when dealing with texts. Symbols and functions exist in all substrates serving as text containers, nevertheless, we often encounter these paleographic, codicological, philological, and linguistic terms not in a well-defined way, but quite empirically, due to two significant issues:

- Symbols and functions are taxonomically complex, and they demand a large amount of effort and research to be well-defined, despite the existence of bibliographic reference works on Palaeography, Codicology²² and Critical Editing.
- Symbols and functions are firmly connected to the way we perceive manuscripts and handwriting. I mean that from a firm materialistic perspective it is rather the manuscript and the specific strokes a scribe creates as physical objects that bring to existence symbols and functions applied to strokes, and not the opposite. This observation triggers a complexity of paleographic and editorial relationships editors are not always aware of.

To be more specific, imagine a whiteboard, a large whiteboard where one can write whatever needed, and project at the same time a manuscripts for a paleographic course. Imagine also that the whiteboard is divided into three parts: the central one is destined for the projection of the manuscript we are reading from, while on the left part of this whiteboard there is a cladogram depicting a) the strokes a scribe creates while writing a text, b) the material needed for the physical construction of the codex, c) the tools used,

²² Duval (2015: 83).

and d) the persons involved into any phase of the manuscript production²³. The area on the right of this imaginary whiteboard is the most important one: we can gradually construct there the taxonomy of all symbols and functions apparent in a manuscript²⁴. While reading from a manuscript, we are getting familiar to more and more complex relationships concerning the terms apparent in the cladogram on the right with the terms apparent on the left. Both cladograms are expandable, and every time a new paleographic or codicological term emerges according to the manuscript we read from, it is properly added to a branch of our cladogram. All relationships create logical; this experiment held in the DH Lab at the University of Athens and led to a platform we called *Manuscribus*.

Image 11: The two main relational branches that led to the *Manuscribus* platform.

Towards a well-structured Transcription and a well-structured Critical Edition: The *Manuscribus* Editor

We presented *Manuscribus* for the first time during Mid-June 2023 in Athens at the International Conference *Fontes sine quibus non: Interdisciplinary Approaches on Critical Editing, Text Encoding, and Text Mining*. *Manuscribus* is fully web based, free online platform, the basic characteristics of which can be triply summarized:

- It supports the well-defined Transcription as a distinct sub-process of Critical Editing: Transcription allows user to type, that is to create, letters and additional marks as **pinpoints**, allowing in turn one to create all symbol-groups needed, according to the semantics of a text.

²³ Gumbert (2010 draft: 1-9); Maniaci (2002: 58).

²⁴ Arp, Smith, Spear (2015: 95-96).

- It supports variants: many users can transcribe the very same part of a text, thus create parallel readings.

- It supports auto-comparison, that is auto-collation²⁵ of all manuscripts transcribed and annotated, thus automatically proposes a well-defined critical edition.

Manuscribus supports all substrates that serve as text-bearers, i.e. independent *folia* and *bifolia*²⁶, rocks, epigraphs, etc., or dependent aggregates such as *codices* and *roll/scrolls*²⁷, permitting the user to add to this expandable list anything needed. Additional information can be given on the dating of a specific substrate; thus, many options have been predicted.

Manuscribus also supports the information needed for a persons' involving in a manuscript: personal information, roles, dates, and places; then one can proceed to the tools a scribe is assumed to have used while creating the handwritten text: a pen, a pencil, a quill, and so on. Tools remain in general unnamed, and *Manuscribus* automatically creates IDs, a practice that is considered useful even for persons, as scribes remain most times unknown. Once the information needed for persons and tools is inserted, a user creates the components comprising a *manus*, a feature that must now considered well-defined.

Image 12: *Manuscribus*' main page.

Manuscribus' layout²⁸ resembles a manuscript but does not mirror it; it visualizes the topological sites²⁹ a manuscript is divided into, including the “main area” and the “margins” – these specific topological areas perceived as having a particular relationship

²⁵ Duval (2015: 83).

²⁶ Maniaci (1996: 125); Maniaci (2002: 73); Gumbert (2010 draft: 26-28); Agati (2017: 143).

²⁷ Maniaci (1996: 71-72); Maniaci (2002: 69); Reynolds, Wilson (1991: 34-35); Agati (2017: 122, 129).

²⁸ Maniaci (2002: 82, 101); Agati (2017: 219).

²⁹ Arp, Smith, Spear (2015: 112); Smith, Varzi (2002: 140).

to the “main” area³⁰, comprising the “header”, the “footer”, the “right margin”, and the “left margin”³¹. *Manuscribus* also visualizes “interlinear” and “intercolumnar”³² spaces, and supports a quite generic category of Textual Criticism: “additions”, that is all the information a scribe notes “above”, “below”, “on the right of”, “on the left of”, or “just after” a specific manuscript area – might be a *mutatio*, a *cancellatio* or a *rasura*³³, for instance. The “over” window is even more interesting, allowing the user to visualize time instances: the *ante* and *post correctionem*³⁴. Finally, a window providing information one might need to define a hand, to see how many rows constitute a text, or to interpret the exact location a manuscript is located in³⁵ are also provided by *Manuscribus*. These are the main features of the Transcription tab, allowing the user to type letters, spaces, and page breaks; for additional symbols a menu provides everything needed.

Once a Transcription process is completed, users can move on to the Annotation process supported by *Manuscribus*, which triggers two additional sub-processes: the Descriptive annotation, which allows users to provide all information on the material entity³⁶ where the transcribed Unicode characters come from – color, hand, number of strokes, and so on –, and the Linguistic annotation, which allows users to generate arrays, that is words, phrases, clauses, sentences, paragraphs, even entire books. *Manuscribus*’ final service lies on the logical inferences deriving from the approximately 9,200 entities that comprise OHT [Ontology for Handwritten Text] – a structured representation of all palaeographic and linguistic entities, that developed during 2022-2023 and served as the *Manuscribus* infrastructure. All inferences deriving from OHT allow users to proceed to critical editing, following one of two scenarios.

- A single-manuscript-process, or
- A multi-manuscript-process, resulting from the collation of two or more manuscripts, following the logical inferences *Manuscribus* is based on.

Following the logical inferences supported by *Manuscribus*, the final representation of both the main text and the *apparatus criticus* is expected to be displayed in a single page.

³⁰ Muzerelle (1985: 331).

³¹ Maniaci (1996: 159-160).

³² Maniaci (1996: 159).

³³ Maniaci (1996: 191, 192); Clemens, Graham (2007: 80); Duval (2015: 78, 131).

³⁴ Arp, Smith, Spear (2015: 124-125).

³⁵ Otte, Beverly, Ruttenberg (2021: 7).

³⁶ Arp, Smith, Spear (2015: 90-95).

Finally, two additional *Manuscribus*' features facilitate a user's work: file copying, and 3D scanning. The first one allows to transcribe just the first manuscript of a whole corpus, in order one to avoid repeating Transcription and Annotation processes from scratch. Once the first manuscript of a corpus is transcribed and annotated, all changes can be inserted manually in any number of copies; thus, it is wrong to assume that no human is involved in Transcription and Annotation. As they comprise reception processes, they need all possible readers to annotate their perception, thus create variants. The second feature facilitating our work with *Manuscribus* involves a 3D scanner, which can recognize the strokes of a manuscript via already established OCR technologies. This 3D scanner was recently published by Springer³⁷.

Conclusion

We can now come to our final conclusions arising from both the theoretical problems we dealt with, and the solution *Manuscribus* suggests:

- Well-defined Critical Editing is a process that lies in two well-defined subprocesses, namely Transcription and Annotation, impossible to achieve without a well-defined relational model supported by digital tools.
- A Critical Edition comprises an “on demand” output, not a static printed document providing limited information on large amount of data perceived by different manuscript readers.
- Any reader of a manuscript is valuable to produce variants, if and only if a system like *Manuscribus* supports a reader's work, permitting to move from theoretical and not well-defined arguments to structured knowledge
- Systems like *Manuscribus* remove all limitations imposed by the well-known critical rule *eliminatio codicum*, and provide us a better knowledge on a *stemma* creation; they even avoid grandiose statements as the *correx* or, even worse, the *ego correxi* statements in an *apparatus criticus*, allowing us to re-estimate the work unknown scribes have produced over centuries.

For centuries we are dealing with structured data and data transformation. If we admit that they are well structured, then yes, Critical Editions can be useful as an inference of

³⁷ Benetos, D., Papadaki, A. et al. (2024).

such a structure. But manuscripts can trigger our most refined data, useful to both people and machines, as no more raffinate data exist worldwide. Artificial Intelligence leads to miracles, while our manuscripts lie in dark repositories or are typed into useless, printed editions.

Abstract

Citing examples from scripts and manuscripts, this paper delineates Transcription and Annotation sub-processes as the substrate of a well-defined Critical Editing, an Ontology-based process recently applied in manuscript analysis. It introduces the *Manuscribus* editor, an innovative and collaborative online platform for manuscript Transcription, Annotation, Collation and Critical Editing, that was developed at the DH Lab [Laboratory for the Management of Greek and Latin Digital Resources], National and Kapodistrian University of Athens (NKUA). *Manuscribus*, launched in mid-2023 and anticipated for release by late 2024 or early 2025, aims to revolutionize scientific work with manuscripts: supporting Transcription and Annotation as distinct processes that demand semantic assertions, *Manuscribus* also supports Collation as logical inference – i.e. well-defined Critical Edition – governed by OTH [Ontology for Handwritten Text], a BFO based Ontology that has been developed in NKUA and comprises the core technology of *Manuscribus* platform.

Keywords

Palaeography; Codicology; Critical editing; Textual Criticism; Stemmatology; Formal Ontologies

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